

IPBES BBA Chapter 4 – Snowball search of the academic field of biodiversity accounting/ IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (Section 4.6)

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Description

This review belongs to the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment, Chapter 4, section 4.6 on methods for interpretation and decision-making. A literature review was based on expert knowledge and a snowball search was conducted as a control step. This snowball search was run using nine initial key papers (seven academic papers, one book, and one book chapter), which were selected due to their relevance in the emerging field of biodiversity accounting. The snowball search resulted in 668 papers and 935 citations, including the initial key records. The data was visualized in both static and dynamic graphs, which allowed experts to visualize the connections between papers (i.e. how papers cite one another) and identify the most cited papers. Additionally, a database was created for all papers cited at least twice. The experts' knowledge, backed up by the snowball search results, enabled authors in Chapter 4 to map the emerging academic field of biodiversity accounting.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Snowball search for articles indexed in OpenAlex
- **Search languages:** Eight initial papers used for the snowball search are in English and one is in French.
- **Search engine:** OpenAlex
- **Exact Search Date:** 13 December 2023
- **Key papers (A):** 9 initial papers (7 academic papers, 1 book, 1 book chapter)
- **Sample extracted:** 668 papers and 935 citations, including the initial key records (B)

Treatment applied: 9 papers (A) were selected by experts using their knowledge in the field of biodiversity accounting as entry points for the snowball search. These papers were selected because they either contained or conducted literature reviews of the emerging field of biodiversity accounting, using different methods and discussing the topic from different perspectives.

This process resulted in an interactive graph showing how the initially selected key papers and the papers cited by these key papers connect to one another (either citing or being cited). A database of papers ranked by the number of citations they received, including only the papers with more than two citations within the corpus (see background document).

Limitations to these results included difficulty identifying books and chapters' cited literature and vice versa, and the impossibility to run the search with grey literature. A large part of biodiversity accounting methods is presented in grey literature, which cannot be searched through the snowball protocol applied here. The snowball search is based on the DOIs of the references, and most grey literature does not have a DOI.

Experts used this search to better map and visualize the extent and consistency of the field (i.e. how much the identified papers refer to one another, thereby consolidating an active and consistent academic discussion), and to identify papers that stand out by being cited more than once.

The papers obtained from the snowball search were then used as part of the qualitative analysis of the literature conducted by experts to identify key debates and underlying controversies in the field.

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_4.6_07-2024_(A)	.csv	24 KB	9 key papers
B	IPBES_BBA_4.6_07-2024_(B)	.csv	520 KB	668 papers